

INQUISITORIAL : TRACING THE DEPARTURE POINT OF THE GOVERNMENTAL SCIENCE IN INDONESIA

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Abstract

This research is a scientific effort to trace the historical footsteps of the birth, growth, and development of Governmental Science in Indonesia. The disclosure of the early phenomenon of science would certainly be the gateway in giving a pure understanding of that science. So that, the result of its inquiry can serve as one of the main sources/ references that provide complete and comprehensive information for further study of Government Science. This study uses a qualitative approach with descriptive type and library research. In this study, the researchers observe the object of research through literature materials, so that the theories underlying the problems in the field under study can be clearly revealed. With the selection of approaches, types, and forms of research, it will certainly be able to reveal in depth how the historical roots of Government Science and emphasize the locus / position of Government Science among other state sciences.

Keywords: *Inquisitorial, Tracing, Government Science, Indonesia*

INTRODUCTION

There is no one who will deny that government has been studied since 400 B.C. Plato (429-347 B.C), known as one of prominent philosophers, has written about government in his book – ‘*Politeia*’. The word ‘*Politeia*’ itself is derived from ‘*polis*’ which means ‘city-state’. So it automatically discusses the city. But it does not talk of city in the sense of region and people, it precisely studies the third element of the city – government. Thus it is reasonable if *politeia* is translated into city-government. Plato’s another book title that is derivation from *polis* is ‘*politikos*’ investigating issues related to government and leadership of the *polis*. His student, Aristotle (384-322 B.C), has written a book as well – *Politica*. The title of this book has polis origin, and also studies about matters of city-state.

By the time, the term of ‘*polis*’ has been changed. For example, it is known as *politic* (English), *politicus/policia* (Latin), *politie* (Dutch), *polizei* (Germany), and *polisi* (Indonesia). Discussions of this matters can be found in the work of Kranenburg (1950) in Surianingrat (1980) demarcating the term of “*politik*” as “*de kunst om de polis, de stad, te besturen*” where as these can be understood as “arts to govern the *polis*” – city. In the end of 17 century, Montesquieu, who has full name – Charles Secondat Baron de Lebrede et de Montesquieu, has proposed the idea of power separation in his own book, *L’Esprit de Lois* (the Spirit of the Laws) that is further elaborated by Immanuel Kant as *Trias Politica*.

Unfortunately, studies on government, polis, are often named as state studies due to the fact that “*polis*” is interpreted as the “state”. For instance, J.J Von Schmid has copied Plato’s book as *Grote Denkers Over Staat en Recht* (1954) where “*De Staat*” is translated as the state. Governmental studies tend to stress on exercising of power (politics). The relationship between government and its people are always drawn into subordinate position or vertical and hierarchical lines. The government is the ruler while the people is governed object.

Thomas Hobbes (1588-1679), quoted by R. Kranenburg (1950) in his book – *Inleiding In De Vergelijkende Staatrechtswetenschap*, argues that man’s state of nature is always in the condition of all

against, all because of the fear of others in getting respect and honour. In the beginning when the state does not exist yet called as the state of nature by Hobbes, there are endless wars between men. Hobbes named this situation as “*Bellum Omnium Contra Omnes*” that means man’s wars against the other men. Hence the existence of laws is important to enforce justice. Laws are necessary to measure and appraise man’s behaviour (Surianingrat, 1980).

According to historical narratives above, it is time for us to critically examine a crucial question. Can governmental studies be considered as a science?. To clarify this issue clearly, it needs such a deep and systematic research on proper structures of understanding to arrange concluding remarks. And here it is important to trace back historical development of the object.

Research Question

According to explanation above, the research question is how are historical narratives of governmental science in Indonesia ?

Research Objective

This research aims at revealing and explaining historical roots of governmental science in Indonesia.

Literature Reviews

The Essence of Government: Linguistic Approach

In etymology, the word of government can be referred to “command”. It also means mandate, utterance, and decree where all these words can be understood as “instruction” (Endarmoko, 2006). The word “command” itself is equal to *gubernaculum/gubernare* (Latin/Spanish), *kybern* (Greek), and govern (English). So it becomes governing/steering in English and *gubernare* in Latin, and *kybernan* in Greek. In Dutch, it is originated from *besturen* (steering) and *kunde* (skill) (Ndraha, 2003). The diffusion of the word *bestuurkunde* then develops into *bestuurwetenschap*, and *bestuurwetenschappen* (plural form); *weten* means understand, while *schap* is science. If both words are combined together, it becomes *wetenschap* which has meaning as science. The definition of government is also explained in Black’s Law Dictionary saying: “From the Latin *gubernaculum*. Signifies the instrument, the helm, whereby the ship to which the state was compared, was guided on its course by the “gubernator” or helmsman, and in that view, the government is but an agency of the state, distinguished as it must be in accurate thought from its scheme and machinery of government” (Black’s Law Dictionary, 1979).

According to several definitions above, it can be formulated systematically in proper meaning consisted of: (1) govern+ing (having control or rule over oneself); (2) government (the office, authority or function of governing); (3) governance (the activity of governing); (4) governability (phenomena or the results of governing activities). The phrase ‘having control or rule over oneself’ means that a condition where someone has awareness of directing, controlling and ruling things. The office, which has authority or function of governing, is governmental institutions or agencies possessing function in governing especially instruction, control and regulation. The activity of governing can be understood as tasks in guiding, managing and regulating accompanied by authority. And phenomena or the results of governing activities are consequences of instruction, control and regulation producing realities often considered as social facts (Gafar, 2015).

The Essence of Government: Scientific Approach

In law literature, the meaning of government is widely defined in two sense – wider and narrow meaning. In the first definition, government consists of *Trias Politica* introduced by Montesquieu in 1748 (Fahmal, 2006) where it is separated into three different powers: (1) legislative power (*la puissance legilative*) in formulating laws; (2) executive power (*la puissance executive in exercising laws*); (3) judicative power (*la puissance de juger*) in administering justice.

Another view comes from Van Vollenhoven (1934) in his book, *Staat Recht Over Zee*, also defining the government in wider concept (*bewinvoering=regeren*), by adding power of police into three power branches of Montesquieu known as “Four Set Up of Montesquieu” or “ Four Territory of Jurisdiction (*Catur Praja*)”. This separation is named as *viermachtenscheiding* including: (1)

Bestuurrecht (power exercising); (2) *politierecht* (police's power); (3) *Rechtspraak/justitierecht* (judicial power); (4) *Regel geven/regelaarsrecht* (power to legalize laws). But Lemaire (1952) in his book, *Het Recht in Indonesie*, analyzes government implementation till he concludes that power is not divided into three or four branches, but it contains five elements: (1) *Wetgeven* (passing the laws); (2) *Rechtspraak* (court); (3) *Bestuur* (government); (5) *Bestuurzorg* (government tasks). At last, Van Poelje Commission in 1972 has mentioned in a research report that government can be defined in wider and narrow concepts. First, government in wider sense is interpreted as function including activities and policies taken by governmental bodies (*bestur organen*) to achieve state's goals. Second, government in narrow meaning in accordance with Montesquieu's *Trias Politica* and Van Vollenhoven's Four Jurisdiction (*Catur Praja*) is consisted of executive power (*bestuur* = actors in exercising power), and it does not contain legislative, court, and police (Fahmal, 2006).

The meaning of government has gradually developed, and scholars have contributed research and investigation in defining government and governance, for example: (1) Herman Finner (1949) in *Theory and Practice of Modern Government* has said that government is politics and administration; (2) C. F. Strong (1960) in *Modern Political Constitutional* has said that government is organization where it has rights to exercise power and sovereignty; (3) Samuel Edward Finer (1974) in *Comparative Government* has argued that first is the activity or the process of governing; second is state of affairs; thrd is people charged with the duty of government; and fourth is the manner, method or system by which a particular society is governed. (4) S. Pamudji (1983) in *Kepemimpinan Pemerintahan di Indonesia* (Governmental Leadership in Indonesia) has said that government is power to rule a country or highest institution which governs a state just like the Cabinet; (5) Bayu Suryaningrat (1980) in *Mengenal Ilmu Pemerintahan* (Inroducing Governmental Science) has said that men or agencies running the government; (6) Taliziduhu Ndraha (2003) in his monumental work, *Kybernologi (Ilmu Pemerintahan Baru)*, argues that government is social phenomena which mean that there is relationships among groups of society whether persons, groups and persons, or *vice versa*.

According to literature reviews above, we come into an understanding that governmental science, according to ontology and epistemology, has been thorough the process of life cycle of science where it has phases, principles and laws of scientific inventions just like requirements in academic environment. Afterwards it is the tasks of scholars on governmental science to develop applied approaches (*aksiologis*) and its uses for man's civilization through research activities where information on government phenomena can be collected to explain and produce knowledge on this matter in systematic, methodical, coherent ways.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Approaches in this research use qualitative-descriptive methods directing this investigation to the specific description on certain phenomena in the form of library research located at Institute of Home Affairs Government (IPDN) libraries in Jakarta and Jatinangor, West Java. The researchers observes objects by examining literature and conducting interviews with experts. So theories can be revealed clearly. By choosing this research approach, it is able to analyze deeply the origin and development of historical roots of government science in Indonesia.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The development of Governmental Science in Indonesia cannot be separated from the implementation of Dutch-Indies colonial rule in Indonesia. At this time various understanding of government began to be introduced by the Dutch-Indies Government in implementing the effective governance. Long period of colonialization by Dutch made many aspects of the prevailing Dutch system of government (which generally embraced the French / German system) also applied in Indonesia. Therefore this system has a real influence in the implementation of government in Indonesia today. In addition, the shift also occurs through the transmission of the culture and science, the development of government in the Netherlands since the era of *Kameralism* until the birth of *Bestuurswetenschap* and

Bestuurswetenschappen in the 20th century gave a great amount of influence on the development of thought about governance in Indonesia.

At the end of the nineteenth century, the Dutch-Indies Government established an educational institution to educate the candidates of civil servants in several parts of Indonesia, and then the Dutch East Indies Government attracted to develop higher education at the OSVIA level (*Opleiding School Voor Inlands Ambtenaren*). This school received primary school graduation. In 1950, OSVIA was upgraded to MOSVIA (*Middelbaar van Inheemse Ambtenaren School*) which received *Mulo* graduates (*Meer Uitgebreid Lager Onderwijs/Broader Basic Education*) where it was equivalent to Junior High School today.

A competent and well-qualified OSVIA graduate could continue his studies at Bestuurschool for 2 years in Jakarta. The school educated the students to be a civil service official at the level of Vice of Regent (*Patih*). Furthermore, the school was upgraded to *Bestuur Academie* in Jakarta as a part of *Rechtshogeschool* (Law Higher School) on the basis of its educational style to the field of law whose purpose is to prepare the personnel as *pangreh praja* leaders.

After becoming an independent nation, Indonesia received influence from the *Anglo-American* government system, as well as receiving influence from the development of the Science of Public Administration. One aspect of the French or German governmental system applied is an attempt to create a powerful central government, which can control the authority of regional and local governments. For that reason, the deconcentration principle was created and entrusted to a special civil servant corps named *Binnenlands Bestuurscorps*, then it changed becoming *Pangrehpraja*. And since Indonesia became an independent nation it was renamed as *Pamongpraja*.

The field of *kepomongprajaan* is the main function of the government which is organized according to the principle of deconcentration, a principle which is still used as one of the main pillars for the implementation of government in Indonesia till nowadays, in addition to other principles, namely the principle of decentralization and the principle of auxiliary (*medebewind*). As the implementation of the principle of deconcentration, the central government delegates the authority of its government to officials dispersed throughout the territory of the Republic of Indonesia, and they are organized in a pyramidal hierarchy. The ultimate goal is to create an effectiveness of governance based on the idea that governmental tasks will be better implemented if the government is done closer than if it was run afar (Pamudji, 1985).

The task of the *Pamongpraja* is to organize all government affairs which have not been submitted to an autonomous region yet and to organize matters which are not included in the duties of one of the government's technical departments. Moreover, it is in charge of leading and managing a territory in order that all government activities in the region become an integrated activity, especially coordination between the agencies and related parties. Besides, the *Pamongpraja* also has the duty to uphold and maintain public order. And most importantly, it is to open access/road in order to be able to relate well with the people in general, ranging from notices, all sorts of orders, directions, and accept all their complaints and desires.

After the proclamation of independence, the *Pamongpraja* Corps participated actively in the efforts to realize the system of government of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia based on Pancasila. Officially, the loyalty of the corps was expressed in their meeting in Solo in early 1946. But in further developments, the circumstances that occurred during the Indonesian people's struggle against the Dutch military aggression in 1947 and the second aggression in 1948 and 1949 made the *Pamongpraja* to be forced to step aside with the guerrilla wars together with the Indonesian National Army (TNI) and the peoples. So the Dutch military was only able to occupy the cities and control the streets during the course of the day. In this phase, many civil services of the Republic of Indonesia known as *Pamongpraja* at that time were killed on the battlefield.

These conditions caused various problems. First, many *pamongpraja* positions became vacant in the high echelons and the lower echelons of positions in high echelons (occupied by the higher rank and the higher-middle rank officials), which originally were held only by the Dutch (and later by the Japanese). Because of emergency, these positions had to be filled by officials who were taken from the lower echelons, with qualifications that were certainly insufficient. The vacancy positions that arose in the lower echelons had to be filled by officials who were taken from the lower echelons, and

so on. So there was a kind of forced promotion involving all echelons without regarding the qualifications.

The second problem was the continuation of the first problem caused by the number of vacancies occurred because many officials were killed or displaced. So the vacancies should be filled by qualified personnel for the sake of continuing the struggle. Although their education was inadequate, they were accepted in an atmosphere of struggle at that time, especially their courage in leading the struggle against the Dutch. In essence, the *pamongparaja* was emergency personnel, appointed directly by supervisors, although these officers (supervisors) formally often had no authority to appoint them. Thus, many civil servants of the Republic of Indonesia at that time had emergency certification. In the meantime, the federal government in its occupied territories also appointed government officials (still called *Pangrehpraja*), many of them were also emergency and subsequently since the founding of the Republic of the United States of Indonesia (RIS), the appointments were also carried out by either the government of the United States of Indonesia or regional government in all over Indonesia territory.

Of course, it was understandable that the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia which replaced the Republic of the United States of Indonesia in the early 1950s faced various problems in its implementation, such as how to prepare an apparatus in the field of government that was not only capable in conducting domestic government affairs but also accepted by the public. And this was the main problem faced by the Ministry of Home Affairs at that time. In the early stages, the factor of acceptability was the main requirement. But right after that, it is only the capability factor that took precedence to get qualified personnel in the field of government, then initiated and developed the *Kepamongprajaan* education. Actually, this was well done since the education that existed before 1949, namely the *Pamongpraja* High School in Solo and the *Pamongpraja* Secondary School in Purwokerto, whereas each of two schools consisted of only one generation, and of course it was not extremely significant to fill low-level officials. Moreover the empty lower-ranking officials had to be filled by the person who got the appropriate education. Therefore, the shortage of educated personnel especially in sub-districts and regencies became very large.

To fulfill the need for middle-ranking civil servants, actually on March 15, 1948, before the Dutch military aggression II, the Academy of Political Science (AIP) was established in Yogyakarta. AIP consisted of three departments, namely Department of Internal Affairs, majoring in Foreign Affairs, and majoring in Publicity. Although the situation was still surrounded by the atmosphere of war and revolution, the Ministry of Internal Affairs at that time sent a number of civil servants in the Department of Home Affairs for the task of studying in AIP. This AIP was also one of the pioneers of the establishment of Gajah Mada University on 19 December 1949 in Yogyakarta, especially the formation of the Faculty of Law, Economics, Social and Political Science (HESP) as mentioned in the previous paragraph.

In its development based on Government Regulation No. 23 of 1949, AIP was dissolved and integrated into the University of Gajah Mada in Yogyakarta because the Academy of Political Science was included as part of social and political sciences, law, and economics which was jointly formed into Faculty of Law, Economics, Social and Political Sciences abbreviated as HESP in *Bahasa Indonesia*. The teaching methods of the Social and Political divisions in the HESP faculty were much influenced by law. Teaching staffs were dominated by lecturers who had the legal background for their subjects of government majors colored by law subject. In 1951, the Ministry of Home Affairs recruited 200 students (read: *Praja*) and Civil Servants assigned to attend lectures at the Faculty of Law, Economics, Social and Politics at Gajah Mada University majoring in Government. Then the Faculty of HESP divided into three new faculties, the Faculty of Law, the Faculty of Economics and the Faculty of Social and Political Sciences. By issuing the Decree of the Minister of Education, Teaching and Culture No. 5379 / Kab on 15 September 1955, the social and political divisions were separated from the HESP faculty into Social and Political faculties. Based on this background, Soerjosoedarmo (1985) concluded that:

1. In the beginning, the Dutch-Indies Government established educations of varying degrees to prepare government officials. The courses given were highly colored by law coupled with practical knowledge. But the course of Government Science itself was not known at the time

2. After Indonesia's independence and establishment of the AIP, Department of Governmental Science was then resumed after integrated with Gajah Mada University. It is worth to note that: (a) Governmental Science began to be given; (b) The course is the curriculum of the governmental department, especially the subject of law science; (c) After obtaining assistance from the International Cooperation Administration (ICA-AID) of the United States and its experts and public administration experts, the Public Administration course began to color the governmental science. So it was deemed necessary to open up the majors of State Administration science, besides reviving the department of Government Science which at that time was still named majors Science of State Administration; (d) After being sent several teachers to England and the United States for doctoral and master programs, the influence of political science on the curricula of the Department of Government science began to increased.

In addition, the Secretary-General of the Ministry of Home Affairs ta about talked Governmental Science to the chancellor and the Head of the Faculty of Social and Politics in Gajah Mada University, essentially whether there was a possibility that the General Political Faculty could develop a special curriculum to fill the needs of the Ministry of Home Affairs to produce a Baccalaureate and Bachelor “plus” in the field of government as a science and *kepomongprajaan* as a sense of art. The term “plus” means that in addition to obtaining sufficient scientific knowledge, the graduates also had a technical skill. So they were ready to perform the duties of the Ministry of Home Affairs or others government agencies in the regions at any time. The final result of the discussion was, the University of Gajah Mada said that it could be done if the curriculum was academically oriented to the development of science on university generally, whereas the practices and techniques that were oriented to the implementation of tasks in the Ministry of Home Affairs required a special institution. As the executor, the Secretary-General of the Ministry of Home Affairs at that time with other people who were deemed experienced in the field of *kepomongprajaan* compiled the curriculum of the Academy of Home Affairs Government (APDN). However, the scientific aspect of APDN curriculum remained oriented to the Faculty of Social and Politics of Gajah Mada University. After the curriculum matured, APDN then was inaugurated in 1956 by the first President of the Republic of Indonesia Ir. Soekarno in Malang, East Java Province (Djaenuri, 2016).

APDN initiated a guided education system at the University level in Indonesia and was the first to adopt a semester system. Compared to the curriculum of the Faculty of Social and Politics of Gadjah Mada University, the APDN curriculum seemed much denser considering the insertions of the practical course as it was described before. The lectures at APDN lasts for 6 semesters (3 years), where the graduates are awarded a Bachelor of Art (BA). The contents are the Baccalaureate “plus” as aspired, a qualification that is considered sufficient for the positions of *kepomongprajaan* included in the lower middle-rank positions and assigned to lead the area and they also deemed capable of becoming administrators of sub-district level government, with other words, capable of serving as sub-district officer. To occupy positions classified as the higher middle-rank positions, and moreover to occupy positions that are classified as the higher-rank position, the APDN graduates must be able to finish their scientific insights without neglecting the features of the mastery of the more technical fields of work indeed intended from the beginning. After the establishment of APDN, it was established further studies, at the bachelor level or called by Doctorandus (Drs) whose the lectures will take about two years. This APDN connection was planned to be established in 1959. This plan had a few obstacles in its realization. But after the birth of the New Order government regime (*Orde Baru/ Orba*) the plan could be realized with the establishment of Institute of Governmental Sciences (IIP) on 25 May 1967 whose establishment was based on Presidential Decree No. RI. 119 The year 1967, in conjunction with the Joint Decree of Minister of Home Affairs and Minister of Education and Culture No.8 year 1967 (Djaenuri, 2016).

Meanwhile, at various state and private universities began to develop a curriculum program that leads to the study of Governmental Science as either a department of a faculty or a part of a Faculty. For Example, the Faculty of Tata Praja Makassar then became one of the important elements of Hasanuddin University in Makassar, wherein 1957 Mr. Tjia Kok Tjiang had been trying to develop Governmental Science with a public lecture entitled “The Meaning and Field of Governmental

Science.” With the establishment of many state universities in the provinces, Government Science has become one of the majors or study programmes in many universities such as Hasanuddin University in Ujung Pandang/ Makassar, Padjadjaran University in Bandung, Diponegoro in University Semarang, Sam Ratulangi University in Manado, Riau University in Pekanbaru, Lambung Mangkurat University in Banjarmasin, Mulawarman University in Samarinda etc (Alfian and Mukmin (ed), 1985). Thus, it can be argued that the Government Science as a science in Indonesia began to be taught after Indonesia's independence. The universities that opened the Department of Governmental Science at the beginning among others are Gadjah Mada University, Padjadjaran University, and Diponegoro University.

Based on the exposure above, historically, government officials or cadres ranging from the center to the regions that have gained special training through the pattern of Teaching, Training and Parenting (*Jarlatsuh*) in the Academy of Home Affairs Government (APDN). And later on, it changed into the College of Home Affairs Government (STPDN). And now it has been changed again into the Institute of Home Affairs Government (IPDN) as a result of the merger with the Institute of Governmental Sciences (IIP) and the College of Home Affairs Government (STPDN) incorporated in a special corps named *Pamongpraja* as a continuation of the corps who have similar duties during the reign of the Dutch-Indies Government, called “*Binnelands Bestuurscorps*” (Dutch period) whereas it was changed to “*Pangrehpraja*” (Japanese period) and later changed to “*Pamongpraja*” (independence era) as mentioned above.

With no intention to rule out the development of Governmental Science in other various universities, the authors try to present the efforts of development and teaching of Government Science at IPDN which is based on dictation books, lecture materials course on master and doctoral level, as well as some papers and writings of IPDN's professors in a number of scientific discussion forums and public lectures we have ever followed. This is based on the consideration that IPDN does participate directly in these efforts (development and teaching of Government Science in Indonesia). In the development and teaching of Government Science at the Institute of Governmental Sciences (IIP), which is the “older brother” of IPDN (before IPDN was born), it required a great attention on matters related to the soul (*geist*) – Tradition, Character, and Operational Objectives of education of Governmental Science Institutions. So the development and teaching of Governmental Science are not misguided. This is very important to note considering the Government Science is classified as not only a science that gives priority to theoretical aspects, but the applied science (*toegepaste wetenschap*) which pays attentions to the practical aspects in the field of government as well.

The emergence of the discourse of the development of Government Science towards the stand-alone science begins with the birth of a kind of applied science ahead of the outbreak of World War II called as “*Bestuurskunde*” where it was pioneered by a Dutch scientist, G.A. Van Poelje, through a book entitled, *Algemene Inleiding tot de Bestuurskunde* (1953), which was translated by Drs. B. Mang Reng Say (1978) under the title “General Introduction to Governmental Science” (*Pengantar Umum Ilmu Pemerintahan*). Then the Governmental Science continues to grow to the present, where the Governmental Science feels that it has been able to become an independent science. When examined in general, the contents of the book Van Poelje seems we can already be convinced that Van Poelje (1953) has been presenting the whole Government Science, and has fulfilled all the requirements to be called as one of the independent branches of applied science, called Government Science. The contents of the book are divided into 9 Chapters which essentially describe the following: (1) Governmental Science as applied science; (2) The establishment and development of Government Science; (3) Government Development; (4) Coordination of Government; (5) Ethics of Government; (6) Government Engineering; (7) Concentration and Differentiation in Each Governance Environment; (8) Civil Service Authority; (9) Government (or governance) and governed.

By looking at the series of journeys above, the development of Governmental Science in Indonesia from the beginning experienced many powerful challenges and obstacles that hampered into an independent scientific discipline. Many other sciences that become the object of his studies related to the symptoms of the government that have been developed before. Even it claims that the Government Science is part of another science, and even some argue that the Government Science is actually not a science that has a Body of Knowledge or the object of learning in particular. But, in the

latest developments, Government Science has been recognized as an independent science whose the object of research is related to the symptoms and practices of government.

In the development and application of Government Science in Indonesia, the existence of Government Science in the world of science need not debate. The development and application of Government Science in Indonesia cannot be separated in relation to the development and application of Government Science in the western countries. It must be admitted, however, that the autonomy of the Government Science in the West was at first also troubled. This is because the phenomenon of government within the framework of state system is studied by a large number of social science disciplines using various approaches (Pamudji, 1983) and (Soewargono, 1995). Soewargono in his inaugural speech as a professor on May 29, 1995, explained about the important role of government in the life of society, as well as the scope of the government's widespread activities. Therefore it requires the existence of Government Science which can function as the backbone for efforts to understand the complex symptoms of today's government. And it is also able to help government organizers to effectively overcome the issues faced by governance. Furthermore, in his other writings – Science of Governance, Governmental Sciences, and Applied Government Science (1995) – Soewargono has explained that today's Government Science is still often seen as a less obvious science figure. It is easy to understand because the Government Science is still relatively young (Soewargono, 1995).

Usually, in every type of science grappling with social issues, the Government Science also seems to face the eternal difficulties of how to meet its intellectual and social relevance. In Ignas Kleden's formulation, it is a choice between being intellectually reasoned and reasonably intelligible, with the risk of being late in meeting social needs or being socially relevant at the right time with the risk that the thought will be ragged intellectually. Furthermore, the test or test of social relevance is based on the extent of acceptance of it, while the test of intellectual relevance is conducted through the examination of the consistency and validity of mind (Kleden in Musntasyir et al., 2002).

The demand for Government Science to be independent is in line with the development of governance issues in practice at all levels of government often requiring approaches to various governance issues where it can be oriented towards community unity, government institution, power, policy, governance, and how the problem of governance can be managed properly. So the welfare of the community can be achieved. Classically, the most common approach is through an understanding of political science that generates an understanding of government and all phenomena that arise through its scientific branches. From the legal aspect of the symptom, government is approached through constitutional law or legal science of state administration. From this perspective, the idea of government at a new stage is understood as a dominant feature and what the State calls besides coercion as a special form of power to do more. In addition, legal science (originally inseparable from Governmental Science) and sociology are important in addition to other complementary efforts in understanding the relationship between government and government (Labolo, 2007).

Initially, the Government Science was understood as a science that learns how the best way to direct and lead public service. In its development, the Government Science is seen as a science studying how the government service / public service arranged and functioned. While the Indonesian government scholars define Government Science as the study of the symptoms of official rulers in society learning the activities in order to unify the interests and needs of society as a whole in terms of ways (methods), facilities (institutions) and environmental factors containing social, physical, and cultural influences on the success and failure of these efforts (Sumendar Soerjosoewarno in Labolo, 2008). While Musanef explains that Government Science is a science in leading and investigating the elements of inward service and relationships with represented societies, it seeks the best people for every public service as a whole that investigates systematically the problems of centralization, decentralization, coordination, inward and outward supervision. And it is a science that investigates how the relationship between the government and the governed can be arranged correctly. It is also applied science that can conduct public service inquiry in the widest sense, whether the arrangement or organization of tools to perform the duties of the authorities to obtain the methods of working as precisely as possible to achieve the goals of state (Musanef, 1984).

The next othought is the opinion of van Poelje, who gives the following formula: “*Hoogerwerf de bestuurleer als leer van het overheidshandelen*” that is the doctrine of government

as the doctrine of the actions of the government, further explained by Van Poelje in papers of Surianingrat (1985) putting forward in the report of scientific meeting Assessment Science Government on 30-31 July 1985 in Jakarta that: “*de bestuurskunde leert hoe men de openbare dienst het beste inricht en laidt*” where it means that Government Science teaches how to organize and lead the public services as best possible. The other opinion from Mac Iver is almost the same: “there is an important body of systematic knowledge about the state, the conditions under which different types of government emerge, the characteristics of the different types, the relations between the government and the governed in which government carries out on their functions according to their kind, and so forth. This body of knowledge may properly be named as a science”.

Based on the previous exposure and description, it can be simplified as follows. In the beginning, the presence of Governmental Science in Indonesia is normative, positive law, and it was taught as *Pangrehpraja* knowledge further known as civil service. This is called as the *first paradigm* of Government Science. Then since the year of 1940s, there was a change in the curriculum system at the *Pamongpraja* school. In 1947, to prepare civil servants in various government departments, the Academy of Political Science (AIP) was founded in Yogyakarta. One of the majors was the governmental department, where the thoughts of Government Sciences in the past was a science that was familiar with political science. This is the *second paradigm* of Government Science – a strong tradition to date especially within the University of Indonesia. In 1949, the AIP was integrated into UGM and incorporated within the HESP faculty. In 1955, the government department changed its name to the Department of State Business Sciences and then later changed becoming the Department of Public Administration (Public Administration).

In 1960, the Department of Government Science was revived, but the teaching remained in the second paradigm as explain above, because the Government Science taught at APDN Malang organized by the Ministry of Home Affairs and it was opened in 1956 previously closer to the science of state administration combined with the Indonesian government and political science. This combination is what forms the *third paradigm* in Governmental Science. This paradigm persists in a stratum-level teaching system in IIP Jakarta.

When Rudini served as Minister of Home Affairs, there was a change in the governmental system within the Ministry of Home Affairs. The establishment of candidates for department personnel was centered in STPDN Jatinangor through a 24-hour military model of teaching, training, and parenting. This was done in order to strengthen the strategy of reengineering people (REPE) to perpetuate the new order or the Soeharto regime of that era. The teaching of the Government Science incorporated militaristic doctrines. Viewed from the point of the methodical and didactical, this change is called the *fourth paradigm* of Governmental Science, circa 1993/1994.

Afterward, the Training Agency of Ministry of Home Affairs established Government Management Development Center. Literally, the teachings of management enriched the Government Science. But that teaching has not been able to contribute to the centralistic bureaucratic machinery of the time. The definition of government management in the relationship is seen through the scope of the subject matters of its curricula – the principle and system of government, governance law, ecological governance philosophy and ethics of government; the practice of governance, government leadership, regional development reform. However, state-of-the-art Government Science with these nuances has entered the *fifth paradigm* of government management.

In the 1990s, to anticipate global change and reform in Indonesia, the Institute of Governmental Science (IIP) continued the new thinking about Governmental Science that has been pioneered since the 1930s. If the first Government Science was taught as a science or knowledge of the government officials, because the participants are the civil servants or government officials. But now it conducted an assessment of the change of Government Science into the knowledge of the ruled people. This thinking is fully supported by University of Padjajaran (UNPAD) in Bandung. Then UNPAD and IIP held Master Program of Social Sciences of Study Area (BKU) Governmental Science in 1996, and Doctoral Program in Social Sciences with the concentration of Governmental Science in 2000. Governmental Science developed through those programs are Governmental Science which departs from humans back to humanity, whereas it is based on reinventing government premises, and more familiar with sociology and management, and developed into the science of his ruling people named

as Kybernology. This is the *sixth paradigm* of Government Science. In the next development, the Decree of the Minister of Education and Culture No. 47 / E / 0/2013 dated February 12, 2013 allows IPDN to open the Doctoral Program of Governmental Science separately, and it implies that Governmental Science as an independent science finally gains recognition in Indonesia.

Furthermore, the authors can explain that when the formulation of Governmental Science compiled from various angles of view, the Government Science can be defined as follows: (1) Governmental Science learns the symptoms of government; (2) Governmental Science is a science that learns all the government activities in the implementation of its duties; (3) Governmental Science learns, analyzes, and observes all actions of the government in carrying out its functions; (4) The Governmental Science is the knowledge of governing and governability, it learns the institutions of society, the forms, and systems of government, the activities of governments concerned with laws and regulations determining political policies, and studies the problems of governance, behaviour of government.

From several definitions and explanations above, it can be concluded that the Government Science essentially studies the symptoms of the government that involves the government as an organization that organizes the government, government activities that include the main tasks and functions of government and governed in this case the people who inhabit a State. These three concepts form a linkage that becomes the boundary of governmental science. Of course, these relate to theories pertaining to the phenomenon of government which had previously been developed by other state sciences such as political science, State administration as well as law science although the latter is not included in the States sciences. But, in the development of Government Science at first, this science is very closely related. There are many approaches used by Government Science in studying the symptom of government using an approach of law science.

The governance symptom that is the target of Governmental Science when it is associated with the administration of government is strongly related to the praxis of the government administration. And there is even the opinion that the Governmental Science is based on the practice of governance. The birth of Governmental Science can occur due to intellectual demands and social demands. In the birth of Government Science, the history of science shows that the Government Science was born out of social necessity (social relevance) rather than intellectual relevance. This social relevance is very prominent, evidenced by the fact that the birth of Government sciences is intended to address governance issues.

Based on the above explanation, it can be argued that the Government Science is a field of study that gives the main attention to the symptoms and practices of government, commonly referred to as general government. With such attention, Government Science works to understand, exposure, and explain the phenomena and practices of the government, both in the material sense and in the sense of process. The materials and process aspects of the symptoms and practices of government in a State are manifested in the activities and relations of government. Government activities reflect the movement or efforts made by the government on the State to realize the prosperity and happiness of all people, while government relations describe the atmosphere of interconnection between the government and the people and the environment. Thus, Government Science can be expressed as a Science that learns the preparation and management of government activities and their impact on the relationship between the government, the people, and the environment.

CONCLUSSION AND RECOMENDATION

From the results of processed research data, the conclusion that can be drawn is that basically government science has navigated the trajectory of a very long historical journey and the process in the life cycle of science in accordance with the stages in the principles and laws of scientific discovery. But the hallmark of a science is dynamic, where this means that there must be an ongoing effort and endeavor from the pioneers / experts, supporters, and users of the science in questions. So the existence of that science is maintained.

Based on the existing situation and condition, the strengthening of ontology, epistemology, and axiology of Government Science must get enough portion. So the real identity of Government Science

will still stand firmly, while we conduct the study and further study of interdisciplinary genre, multidisciplinary, even transdisciplinary. So the usefulness of Science the government towards the civilization of mankind is increasingly perceived.

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